

“METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF AN RP-HPLC METHOD FOR DETERMINATION OF ANTIDIABETIC AGENTS IN PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM”

Dr. Madhuri A. Theng^{1*}, Dr. Ashutosh K. Dash².

¹Assistant Professor Pharmacology Department Gawande College of Pharmacy, Lavala road, Sakharkerda, Dist Buldana MS Maharashtra, India-443203

thengmadhuri7@gmail.com

²Principal of Gawande College of Pharmacy, Lavala road, Sakharkerda, Dist Buldana MS Maharashtra, India-443203

Abstract:

In this study, a new High-performance liquid chromatographic (RP-HPLC) approach was developed for the simultaneous measurement of Remogliflozin and Pioglitazone in bulk and tablet dosage form. The method was validated using various parameters such as linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, LOD, and LOQ. The new approach demonstrated good linearity in concentration ranges of 66-330 µg/ml for Remogliflozin and 10-50g/ml for Pioglitazone, respectively, with linear regression coefficients ($r^2 = 0.9996$ and 0.9995). The LOD and LOQ for Pioglitazone in were calculated to be 0.55g/ml and 1.674g/ml, respectively, and 2.80g/ml and 8.485g/ml for Remogliflozin. The low % RSD figures imply that the approach is precise and accurate.

The developed RP HPLC method was found to be linear over a wider concentration range, and it can be used for routine qualitative and quantitative analysis of Remogliflozin and Pioglitazone in bulk and tablet dosage form and validated according to ICH guidelines. As a result, the proposed method is easily applicable for routine analysis studies for monitoring the assay in the pharmaceutical industry. In conclusion, the developed RP HPLC approach is reliable, accurate, and precise and can be used for the simultaneous determination of Remogliflozin and Pioglitazone in bulk and tablet dosage form. The proposed method can be a valuable tool for quality control and routine analysis in the pharmaceutical industry.

Keywords: RP HPLC, Remogliflozin, Pioglitazone, precision, robustness, LOD, and LOQ.

Introduction

Analytical Chemistry is defined as “The science and the art of determining the composition of materials in terms of the elements or compounds contained.” This branch of chemistry, which deals with both theoretical, practical science and is practiced in a large number of laboratories in many diverse ways. Methods of analysis are routinely developed, improved, validated, collaboratively studied and applied. In analytical chemistry, it is of prime importance to gain information about the qualitative and quantitative composition of substances and chemical species that is to find out what substance is composed and exactly how much. In quantitative analysis the question is how much is present. The research work in this thesis is based on this criterion. Pharmaceutical analysis deals not only with medicaments (drugs and their formulations) but also with their precursors i.e. with the raw material on which degree of purity and quality of medicament depends. The quality of the drug is determined after establishing its authenticity by testing its purity and the quality of pure substance in the drug and its formulations^{1,2}.

Chromatography “Chromatography is defined as a procedure by which solutes are separated by a dynamic differential migration process in a system consisting of two phases, one of which moves continuously in a given direction and which the individual substances exhibits mobilities by reasons of difference in adsorption, partition, solubility, vapor pressure, molecular size or ionic charge density.” [6] High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) was developed in the late 1960s and early 1970s. Today it is widely applied for separation and purification in a variety of areas including pharmaceuticals, biotechnology, environmental, polymer and food industries. High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) was known as high pressure liquid chromatography. It is a form of column chromatography in which the stationary phase consist of small particle (3-50 μm) packing contained in a column with a small bore (2-5mm), one end of which is attached to source of pressurized liquid eluent (Mobile phase). The technique offers major improvements in speed, resolving power, detection, quantification, convenience and applicability to new sample types. Modern HPLC techniques became available in 1969, but from 1990s HPLC become most popular instrument for drug analysis which is presently used in pharmaceutical research and development ⁶. Following are some important types of HPLC:⁷⁻⁹

A. Based on modes of chromatography

- Normal phase mode
- Reverse phase mode

B. Based on principle of separation

- Adsorption chromatography

- Ion exchange chromatography
- Ion pair chromatography
- Gel permeation chromatography
- Affinity chromatography

C. Based on elution technique

- Isocratic separation
- Gradient separation

D. Based on the scale of operation

- Analytical HPLC
- Preparative HPLC

E. Based on the type of analysis

- Qualitative analysis
- Quantitative analysis

RP-HPLC (Reverse Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography)

Reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) involves the separation of molecules on the basis of hydrophobicity. The separation depends on the hydrophobic binding of the solute molecule from the mobile phase to the immobilized hydrophobic ligands attached to the stationary phase, i.e., the sorbent. The solute mixture is initially applied to the sorbent in the presence of aqueous buffers, and the solutes are eluted by the addition of organic solvent to the mobile phase. Elution can proceed either by isocratic conditions where the concentration of organic solvent is constant, or by gradient elution whereby the amount of organic solvent is increased over a period of time.¹⁰

The primary objective of research project is to develop Chromatographic Method for antidiabetic drugs in pharmaceutical dosage formulation

To develop Simple, Accurate, and Precise- HPLC method for estimation in pharmaceutical dosage form

To perform Validation of Developed Method as per ICH guidelines like Specificity, Precision, Linearity, Accuracy, LOD, LOQ, Robustness and Ruggedness etc.

Drug Profile:-**Fig 1:** Structure of Remogliflozin**1.REMOGLIFLOZIN****Table1: Physical Parameter of Remogliflozin**

Parameter	Value
Molecular Formula	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ FO ₄ S
Molecular Weight	418.52 g/mol
Appearance	White to off-white powder
Solubility	Soluble in DMSO, slightly soluble in water
Melting Point	152-156°C
pKa	13.34
Storage Conditions	Store at room temperature, protected from light and moisture

2.LINAGLIPTIN

Linagliptin medication primarily used to management type 2 diabetes mellitus.

Chemical Properties**Fig 2:** Structure of Linagliptin

IUPAC Name:(±)-5-[[4-[2-(5-Ethyl-2-pyridinyl)ethoxy]phenyl]methyl]-2,4- thiazolidinedione

- **Chemical Formula:**C₁₉H₂₀N₂O₃S
- **Molecular Weight:**356.44 g/mol¹².

Plan Of Work A. Selection of drug a. By literature and market survey. B. Selection of Analytical Technique C. Analytical Method Development and Validation by HPLC Method. 1) 2) 3) 4) Selection of mobile phase. Selection of suitable detection wavelength. To develop method for analysis of pharmaceutical dosage form To perform validation study as per ICH guidelines.

Materials And Method

Table 2.Chemicals Used:

Chemicals	Discription
Remogliflozin :	Remogliflozin : Remogliflozin is an oral antidiabetic medication used to treat type 2 diabetes mellitus. It belongs to the class of sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitors.
Linagliptin :	Linagliptin : Linagliptin is a dipeptidyl peptidase-4 (DPP-4) inhibitor used in the treatment of type 2 diabetes mellitus. It helps lower blood glucose levels by increasing the levels of incretin hormones.
Methanol:	Methanol: Methanol is a polar organic solvent commonly used in analytical techniques and liquid chromatography. It is miscible with water and has good solvating properties.
Buffer solution (0.1% OPA):	Buffer solution (0.1% OPA) : Buffer solution refers to a solution containing ortho phosphoric acid (OPA) in a specific concentration. It is used to adjust the pH and provide buffering capacity in chromatographic methods.
Ortho Phosphoric Acid :	Ortho Phosphoric Acid :Ortho Phosphoric Acid, also known as phosphoric acid, is a mineral acid used in various applications, including as a pH adjuster and buffer in analytical chemistry and chromatography.
Triethylamine :	Triethylamine :Triethylamine is a volatile and highly basic organic compound often used as a mobile phase additive in liquid chromatography. It helps adjust pH, reduce peak tailing, and improve separation in certain applications.

Selection of solvent/Solubility parameter

The solubility of Remogliflozin and Linagliptin in were checked in various solvents. Both Remogliflozin and Linagliptin in are soluble in methanol. Hence methanol was selected for the further analysis.

Selection of wavelength for analysis

The wavelength selected for the estimation of Remogliflozin and Linagliptin in is 215nm with the highest absorption peak intensities. Further simultaneous determinations were performed at this wavelength¹⁸.

Procedure for Buffer PreparationTo prepare a buffer solution with a specific molar concentration and pH, we first selected appropriate components, such as a weak acid and its conjugate base or a weak base and its conjugate acid. For instance, in preparing a phosphate buffer, we used monobasic potassium phosphate (KH_2PO_4) and dibasic sodium phosphate (Na_2HPO_4). We determined the desired molar concentration; for a 0.1 M phosphate buffer, we calculated the amounts of monobasic potassium phosphate and dibasic sodium phosphate needed. We began by dissolving the required amount of monobasic potassium phosphate in distilled water. Then, we added the required amount of dibasic sodium phosphate to this solution. We adjusted the final volume to 1 liter with distilled water. We used a pH meter to check the pH of the solution and adjusted it if necessary by adding small amounts of HCl or NaOH to reach the desired pH. For example, to prepare 1 liter of a 0.1 M phosphate buffer at pH 7.4, we weighed 9.078 g of monobasic potassium phosphate and 10.723 g of dibasic sodium phosphate. We dissolved these in approximately 800 mL of distilled water, adjusted the pH to 7.4 using HCl or NaOH, and then diluted the solution to a final volume of 1 liter with distilled water²⁰.

Preparation of stock standard solution

Exactly, 66 mg of Remogliflozin and 10 mg Linagliptin in standards were weighed separately and dissolved into two different 100ml of calibrated volumetric flask containing 50ml of methanol, sonicated for 10minutes. Finaly volume make upto calibrated mark obtaining 660ug/ml and 100ug/ml of Remogliflozin and Linagliptin in standard solution.

Preparation of working standard solution

A working standard solution of Remogliflozin and Linagliptin in were prepared by diluting accurate volume of 1.0 mL into 10 mL of two different calibrated volumetric flask from standard stock solutions and volume was diluted upto the mark to get the 66 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ concentrations of Remogliflozin and Linagliptin in. Selection of chromatographic layer The RP-HPLC was selected to achieve the objectives of the development of a stability

indicating assay method²¹.

Methods: The various instrumental methods developed and validated in the current study were based on RP-HPLC RP-HPLC Method: The RP-HPLC method for one combination was developed based solubility and polarity of sample. Since the combination of drugs selected were soluble in polar solvents a RP-HPLC stationary phase was selected. Based on PKa / PH values of drugs various organic solvents were tried and the system that gave ideal separation and symmetric peaks were selected for the study. The mobile phase were prepared freshly, filtered and sonicated for 30 minutes prior to use in order to deareate the mobile phase. The column was equilibrated for 30-40 minutes with mobile phase prior to injection of sample. The volume of injection was 20 ul. The system suitability parameter that are critical to the analytical separation and quantification were carefully evaluated throughout the study. The various chromatographic separation were developed by changing parameters included fixing of chromatographic conditions. The optimized method was developed and validated as per ICH recommendations.(Q2R1) Method Validation: The developed method was validated according to the International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines for validation of analytical procedures²².

Linearity

The ability of the method to obtain test results proportional to the concentration of the analyte within a given range. It was evaluated by linear regression analysis, which was calculated by the least square regression method.

Accuracy

Accuracy can be defined as the closeness of agreement between a test result and the accepted reference value. Accuracy of the method was determined by recovery study. Analytical method may be considered validated in terms of accuracy if the mean value is within $\pm 20\%$ of the actual value.

Limit of detection

The limit of detection (LOD) is the lowest concentration of analyte in a sample that can be detected but not necessary quantified. $LOD = 3.3 \times \sigma / S$ Where, σ = the standard deviation of the response and S= slope of the calibration curve.

Limit of quantitation

The limit of quantitation is the lowest concentration or amount of analyte that can be determined quantitatively within an acceptable level of repeatability precision and trueness. Where, σ = the standard deviation of the response and S= slope of the calibration curve.

Precision

The precision of the method was determined repeatability (intra-day) and intermediate (inter

day) Precision and was expressed as RSD of series of measurements. Intra-day precision was evaluated by six replicated reading at three concentration levels within the linearity range. Inter-day precision was studied by comparing the results on 3 different days.

Table 3:Physical characterization

Description	Nature	Crystallinesolid
	Colour	Whiteto off-white
	Odour (smell)	Characteristic
	Solubility	Solublein methanoland ethanol

Confirmation of drug by Melting point

Table 4:Melting point

Standard range	Reported range
216 – 219	216 -218

Fig 3:FT-IR Spectrum of Remogliflozin

Table 5:FT-IRofRemogliflozin

Functional group	Standard range (cm^{-1})	Observed value(cm^{-1})
C – F stretching	1400 – 1000	1334.78
C – H	1450	1427.37
N– H stretching	3350 – 3310	3317.67
C =N stretching	1690 – 1640	1635.69

Confirmation with FT-IR Spectrometer Physical characterization:

Confirmation with UV/Vis-Spectrophotometer

Fig 4: UV-Vis-Spectrum of Remogliflozin

Linagliptin

Table 6:Physical characterization

Description	Nature	Solid
	Color	Crystalline solid
	odor (smell)	Odorless
	Solubility	Soluble in methanol and ethanol

Table 7:Melting point

Standard range	Reported range	Observed range
239 °C	224 – 226 °C	228 – 230 °C

Confirmation with FT-IR Spectrometer

Fig 5:FT-IR Spectrum of Linagliptin

Table 8:FT-IR of Linagliptin

Functional group	Standard range(cm ⁻¹)	Observed value(cm ⁻¹)
C=O stretching	685 – 1666	1687.77
C – Cl stretching	550 – 550	848.71
O– H stretching	550 – 3200	3255.95
N– H stretching	350 – 3310	3362.04

Confirmation with UV/Vis-Spectrophotometer

Fig 6: UV-Vis-Spectrum of Linagliptin

Table 9:Linearity data of Remogliflozin

Name of Drug Remogliflozin		
Sr.No.	Concentrationin($\mu\text{g.m L}^{-1}$)	Peak Area {n=6}
1	66	3327.02
2	132	5871.61
3	198	8731.47
4	264	11139.20
5	330	13634.20
6	396	16359.46
RegressionEquation		$y=39.33x+758.0$
Correlationcoefficient(R^2)		$R^2 =0.999$
LOQ		8.485 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
LOD		2.80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Table 10:Linearity data of Linagliptin

Name of Drug Linagliptin		
Sr.No.	Concentration in ($\mu\text{g.mL}^{-1}$)	Peak Area {n=6}
1	10	398.76
2	20	794.80
3	30	1134.33
4	40	1481.06
5	50	1873.87
6	60	2240.38
Regression Equation		$y=36.54x+41.32$
Correlation coefficient(R^2)		$R^2 =0.999$
LOQ		1.674 $\mu\text{g/ml}$
LOD		0.55 $\mu\text{g/ml}$

Fig 8: Chromatogram of Remogliflozin and Linagliptin

Table11: Accuracy data of Remogliflozin and Linagliptin

Remogliflozin					
Sr.No.	Accuracy level	Initial Conc.	Amount spiked	Amount recover % Recovery	Statistical Analysis
1	80%	66	52.8	99.78	Mean=99.46 SD=0.31 %RSD=0.31
2		66	52.8	99.16	
3		66	52.8	99.43	
1	100%	66	66	101.07	Mean=100.81 SD=0.34 %RSD=0.33
2		66	66	100.43	
3		66	66	100.93	
1	120%	66	79.2	100.63	Mean=100.64 SD=0.17 %RSD=0.17
2		66	79.2	100.81	
3		66	79.2	100.47	

Linagliptin

Sr.No.	Accuracy level	Initial Conc.	Amount piked	Amount recover % Recovery	Statistical Analysis
1	80%	10	8	99.33	Mean=99.59 SD=0.23 %RSD=0.23
2		10	8	99.77	
3		10	8	99.66	
1	100%	10	10	100.70	Mean=100.46 SD=0.32 %RSD=0.31
2		10	10	100.57	
3		10	10	100.10	
1	120%	10	12	99.51	Mean=99.91 SD=0.37 %RSD=0.37
2		10	12	99.98	
3		10	12	100.25	

Fig 9:HPLC analysis of marketed formulation of tablet (Concentration80%)

Fig 10:HPLC analysis of marketed formulation of tablet(Concentration100%)

Fig 11:HPLC analysis of marketed formulation of tablet(Concentration120%)

Interday /intermediate precision:

Implementing the procedure mentioned under experimental section (5.3), the homologous mixture of Remogliflozin and **Linagliptin** of three replicates of selected similar concentrations; were tested and evaluated in three successive days (interday/intermediate precision). The %RSD was calculated and it is found less than 2%; for all analytes; shown in Table 6.4.1- 6.4.2).

Table 12: Precision data of Remogliflozin

Remogliflozin				
Sr.No.	Conc.	Peak area	Amount found %Assay	Statistical analysis
intraday				
1	132	5997.93	100.88	SD=4.21 %RSD=0.33
2	198	8764.80	102.89	
3	264	11195.75	100.65	
Intraday				
1	132	5976.94	100.48	SD=8.24 %RSD=0.38
2	198	8570.80	100.39	
3	264	11128.45	100.00	

Table 13: Precision data of Linagliptin

Linagliptin				
Sr.No.	Conc.	Peak area	Amount found %Assay	Statistical analysis
intraday				
1	20	791.18	102.24	SD=5.64 %RSD=0.51
2	30	1136.26	99.98	
3	40	1486.05	99.03	
Intraday				
1	20	785.04	101.68	SD=7.45 %RSD=0.70
2	30	1129.44	99.36	
3	40	1487.75	99.15	

Fig 12:Interday Precision of Remogliflozin and Linagliptin 132:20ug/ml

Fig 13:Intraday Precision of Remogliflozin and Linagliptin 198:30ug/ml

Robustness

This studies was determined by small variation in separation parameters like effect of temperature, flow rate, eluent composition, temperature, pH, wavelength, injection volume on selected separation variables including capacity factor (k'), resolution (R_s), tailing factor (T_f), separation factor, theoretical plates (N) and peak area. Therefore, increased the flow rate by +0.1 ml/minutes, marginally reduced the t_R values of all selected drugs and impurities where as reducing it, extended slightly the t_R values of same drugs. Like this each factor selected to examine were changed at two levels (-1, +1) shown in table no 5. Robustness of proposed work was carried out by attempting to make significant changes in % proportion of methanol in solvent system (mobile phase), temperature of column oven compartment, flow rate and wavelength. The influence of each of the independent variables was determined for the peak areas of Remogliflozin and Linagliptin.

Table 14; Robustness data of Remogliflozin and Linagliptin

Sr. No.	Condition/Parameters	Mean Peak Area±SD %RSD for Remogliflozin	Mean Peak Area±SD %RSD for Linagliptin
1	Flowrate(-) 0.7ml/min	0.29	0.71
2	Flowrate(+)0.9ml/min	0.05	0.16
3	Mobile Phase(-) 74+26v/v	0.16	0.52
4	Mobile Phase(+) 76+24v/v	0.12	0.07
5	Wavelength(-)214nm	0.38	0.71
6	Wavelength(+) 216nm	0.20	0.70
7	Temperature30°C	0.28	0.19
8	Temperature40°C	0.37	0.23

Summary And Conclusion:-

In this study, a new High-performance liquid chromatographic (RP-HPLC) approach was developed for the simultaneous measurement of Remogliflozin and Pioglitazone in bulk and tablet dosage form. The method was validated using various parameters such as linearity, accuracy, precision, robustness, LOD, and LOQ. The new approach demonstrated good linearity in concentration ranges of 66-330 µg/ml for Remogliflozin and 10-50g/ml for Pioglitazone, respectively, with linear regression coefficients ($r^2 = 0.9996$ and 0.9995). The LOD and LOQ for Pioglitazone in were calculated to be 0.55g/ml and 1.674g/ml, respectively, and 2.80g/ml and 8.485g/ml for Remogliflozin. The low %RSD figures imply that the approach is precise and accurate.

The developed RP HPLC method was found to be linear over a wider concentration range, and it can be used for routine qualitative and quantitative analysis of Remogliflozin and Pioglitazone in bulk and tablet dosage form and validated according to ICH guidelines. As a result, the proposed method is easily applicable for routine analysis studies for monitoring the assay in the pharmaceutical industry.

In conclusion, the developed RP HPLC approach is reliable, accurate, and precise and can be

used for the simultaneous determination of Remogliflozin and Pioglitazone in bulk and tablet dosage form. The proposed method can be a valuable tool for quality control and routine analysis in the pharmaceutical industry.

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Competing Interests: The authors declare no conflict of interest with this research.

Ethical approval: Since no animals were used in this study, Ethical approval was not needed.

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